

IMPROVING THE DEVELOPMENT MODEL OF METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article provides basic ideas about the main stages of the development of methodological skills of teachers of the future primary class, the organizational and operational component, as well as an improved model of the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *competence, methodological qualifications, stages of development of skills, organizational and pedagogical conditions, model.*

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, institutions of Higher Education carry out systematic work on the modern traditions of the mathematical education of primary school teachers, setting tasks, setting new directions of development, determining the general strategy of research and studying new problems that require an appropriate/adequate option of solutions. The main objective of the development of the skills of the teaching methodology of mathematics of future primary school teachers is the implementation of work related to the mobility of the content of school mathematical education. The school is a change in the understanding of the subject of the teaching methodology of mathematics, the main focus in teaching is on the formation of a variety of competencies from the formation of the foundations of mathematical knowledge. Scientific research is also being carried out on the transfer of the universal importance of the science of the methodology of teaching mathematics and mathematical knowledge to the focus on mastering the methods of activities for the application of everyday life, ensuring the priority of the mathematical component of professional education.

One of the directions of scientific and methodological support for the quality of the educational process is the development of the activity of methodological qualifications of teachers of the future primary class. One of the directions of scientific and methodological support for the quality of the educational process is the development of the activity of methodological qualifications of teachers of the future primary class. First of all, in order to learn the algorithm of the process of developing their creativity skills, it is necessary to have an idea of any creative process and the algorithm for its implementation. On the basis of the analysis of the literature, the stages of the process of any methodological qualifications are clarified: determination of the concept that determines the general direction of achieving the solution of the issue; gathering information on determining the condition and solution of the issue; choosing the method of solving the issue and checking it. The process of developing the activity of methodological qualifications of teachers of the future primary class consists of the following stages. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1.

It is advisable to study the organization of research activities in the educational process of developing the activity of methodological qualifications of future primary school teachers from the point of view of a systematic approach. On the basis of a systematic approach, the study developed a model for the development of the activity of methodological qualifications of teachers of the future primary class and identified a set of organizational and pedagogical conditions for its implementation. Based on a systematic approach, a model for the development of methodological skills of future elementary school teachers was developed in the study, and a set of organizational and pedagogical conditions was determined for its implementation. (See Figure 2).

In the improvement of the model, the process of encouraging the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers is considered as a pedagogical system, and the main component that systematizes the process is the target component. The goal: to develop the methodological skills of future elementary school teachers by involving them in their activities in the educational process. So, the main target component that systematizes the proposed model is to help the future primary school teachers to improve their professional skills by involving them in the methodical skills development activities, as well as determine the direction of such activities in the future.

Figure 2. Model of development of methodical skills of future primary school teachers

The next organizational-activity component of the model developed in the research includes the content and principles that determine the organization of pedagogical activity to achieve the set goal and solve the selected tasks.

This component of the system of developing methodical skills of future elementary school teachers is a unity of the purpose, principles, content, organizational forms, methods and tools of teachers and other subjects that ensure their involvement in the activity of methodical skills. These motivating subjects are a system of tools and methods that create opportunities for future primary school teachers to show their interest and participation in the development of methodical skills, and to develop the need to engage in experience.

During the research, it became clear that, from the point of view of a systematic approach, the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers is an interaction between the object, the subject of stimulation and the environmental conditions. is considered a secret system, as a result of which their needs and motives for participation in various forms of professional creativity are developed.

Conclusions:

1. Development of methodological skills of future elementary school teachers within the framework of studying the content of the mathematics teaching methodology course, one of the aspects of developing methodological skills of elementary school teachers is the method of

creating problems/exercises/tasks. it is necessary to solve the educational tasks of mastering step by step;

2. It is necessary to determine the leading rules and features of solving educational tasks that are taken into account in the development of a specific/concrete methodology for the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers.

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